

Contribution from the IE Data Analysis and Reporting Working Group.

Notable Trends in Informatics Bachelor Students' Retention and Graduation Rates across Europe

Premek Brada (University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, Czechia), Ana C. R. Paiva (Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Portugal), Svetlana Tikhonenko (Informatics Europe)

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Introduction

The landscape of European education in informatics, with its diversity, rich traditions and strong roots, has always been an object of interest at Informatics Europe (IE). Among the motivations was the shared need to get a broader, representative picture of this diverse landscape, where individual countries differ in both the structure and details of their higher education (HE) systems and in the ways data about these systems is being collected, categorised and made available. Given its wide coverage of European countries through its members, IE has the unique ability to provide a broader, representative picture.

The results of this interest range from data collection activities through analyses to policy recommendations. Early pivotal examples include the annual series of reports “Informatics Education in Europe: Institutions, Degrees, Students, Positions, Salaries — Key Data Report” [2] and the “Europe cannot afford to miss the boat” report [1]. The data collection efforts took an important step with the creation of the Informatics Europe Higher Education Data Portal¹, launched in 2019 in collaboration with the Software Institute at Università della Svizzera Italiana and later presented in a comprehensive paper [3].

In this article, we briefly cover the Data Portal's features and then present key findings from a recent analysis using its data — trends in

retention and graduation rates among European bachelor-level informatics students.

Informatics Europe Data Portal

The Informatics Europe Higher Education Data Portal, part of the IE public website, provides both statistical and descriptive information on various aspects of higher education in informatics across Europe. The portal contains data on informatics student and graduate numbers (at all three levels of higher education) starting from the academic year 2010/2011, as well as lists of informatics HE institutions and factual information on HE systems in individual countries (focusing on the specifics of the Informatics field), currently covering 25 European countries.

This dataset is curated and updated by the IE office every year with new student and graduate statistics and at appropriate moments with revised descriptive parts. While the IE office plays a key role in this process, collaboration with national contacts (representatives from IE member institutions) is essential as they provide clarifications of locally specific aspects of the data, point to reliable national sources, and supply data updates for countries where it is not available from official institutions.

A major part of the portal's dataset is available exclusively to logged-in users, as part of the services provided to IE members. A useful feature of the portal is the online data

¹ <https://www.informatics-europe.org/data/higher-education>

visualisation tool, which depicts cross-country and time-series comparisons directly on the European map and bar-chart graphs. By specifying the topic of interest (i.e. first-year students, students from all semesters, degrees awarded), the level of education according to the Bologna system – bachelor, master, or doctoral (Ph.D.), institution type (Research Universities abbreviated as RU or Universities of Applied Science (UAS) for the countries where these institutions exist), country, and year, users can generate custom maps and graphs to view recent trends in informatics HE in Europe.

Recent Trends in Student Retention and Graduation Rates

This dataset enabled us in the past year to undertake new analytical studies of retention and graduation rates among European bachelor-level informatics students. By *retention* rate, we mean the proportion of students from a cohort entering a given year of study who remain enrolled and make progress toward their degree, and by *graduation* rate, we mean the ratio between the number of students who graduated in a given year and the size of the cohort of corresponding first-year students. Further details on the methodology for computing retention and graduation rates, including the set of countries selected², are provided in the “European Informatics Retention and Graduation Rate Report” [4].

Our studies on these two features are an important contribution to understanding the patterns of informatics students’ progress through studies, since no dataset from any European country provides this information explicitly. It should be noted, however, that this also means the reported Regarding the **gender differences** in retention rates, there is no uniform pattern across Europe. In most countries, women

figures are approximations. Among the reasons are the simplifying assumption that the duration of bachelor programmes is 3 years, as is typical (though not universal) in many Bologna system countries, and that all bachelor students in their final year complete their studies and graduate from the informatics programme in the given country of study.

One of the main challenges in preparing the dataset was ensuring that the country data was sufficiently mutually harmonised, particularly regarding the definition of “Informatics” as a discipline and its reflection in the nomenclatures used in the available statistics, which vary across national systems.

Below, we present several illustrative findings from these studies, highlighting patterns in retention and graduation rates at the bachelor's level.

The calculated retention rates vary across countries, ranging from 75% to 100%, and the overall trend in the last decade is that of a moderate increase: among the 13 countries studied, 7 show increasing retention (see Figure 1 below) and four a stable trend (Bulgaria, Italy, Portugal, United Kingdom), while retention is decreasing in only 2 countries (Switzerland and the Netherlands) which have one of the highest rates in the studied set.

Figure 1: Bachelor-level retention data and trends in informatics – countries with increasing rates.

² AT = Austria, BG = Bulgaria, CH = Switzerland, CZ = Czech Republic, DE = Germany, EE= Estonia, FI = Finland, IE = Ireland, IT = Italy, NL = the

Netherlands, NO = Norway, PT = Portugal, UK = United Kingdom

exhibit slightly higher retention rates (cf. Figure 2), while in others, men show higher retention, notably in Austria, Switzerland, and Germany. In a further group of countries, the gender differences are small and not statistically clear (Italy, Portugal). Overall, gender gaps are small compared to differences across countries.

Graduation rates show a similar pattern in terms of gender comparison, see Figure 3. An interesting observation is that male graduation rates are higher only in predominantly German-speaking countries.

Figure 2: Gender differences in bachelor-level retention rates in informatics.

Figure 3: Gender differences in bachelor-level graduation rates in informatics.

Regarding the types of universities, our studies uncovered high variability in retention rates at universities of applied sciences (UAS) in countries with very small UAS enrolments. On the other hand, UAS contribute to about ½ of

informatics bachelor graduates in 7 countries studied (i.e., in ½ of our sample), see Figure 4, which highlights the need for appropriate policies to cover both research and applied science universities.

Figure 4: Percentage of UAS informatics bachelor's students enrolled in all semesters.

Conclusion

Our studies of bachelor-level retention and graduation rates in Informatics reveal that, overall, the situation across Europe is gradually improving in both metrics, perhaps as a result of many targeted measures at the institutional, country, and EU levels. The findings also support the “common knowledge” that higher education systems exhibit both commonalities and unique national characteristics.

Further work will be needed to understand the causes of the particular values and/or trends in selected countries, e.g., the rapid improvement in graduation rates in Norway and Ireland. Regarding the data available for studies like ours, the national statistics (and the underlying field-of-study definitions) need to be better understood and aligned across Europe.

References

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